

EFFICACY OF DRAMA IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation: *The article tries to analyse communication as an optimal way to teach and learn foreign language. First, it defines drama in an educational context and explains underlining benefits together with reasons how acting can enhance language skills.*

Key words: *drama, acting, communication, monologue, mime, scenes*

There are various types of techniques that can be applied at the English language lessons and they are usually aimed at developing a particular language skill. But there is one aspect that unites all of them: games are activities which are designed to create friendly atmosphere for pupils and at the same time foster pupils` effective learning.

Quite often if we say drama (in educational context) people understand it as a theatrical performance (usually performed by elementary school learners), stage representation, however in language classes we may use different techniques that develop acting abilities and at the same time communication skills.

Communication is an exchange of information and messages and it is not only about words and phrases but also about body language, gestures, facial expressions, ability to express and “read” the ideas that are “between the lines”, that were not said. Thus using drama allows us to create a real-like situation that involves ideas, emotions, in some cases adaptability and improvisation.

There are various definitions of drama and generally we can say that it is an activity when somebody pretends or portrays themselves as somebody or something else in an unreal situation. As S. Holden states: “It provides an opportunity for a person to express himself through verbal expressions and gestures using his imagination and memory.” 1 Drama techniques have been used in various fields of our lives – religious ceremonies, arts, psychotherapy, sociology in confidence-building-courses etc. In all those

above mentioned situations the aim was to prepare people for various situations, to give them language and help them to show or hide feelings and at the same time to read them. It is closely connected with the communication.

Using drama techniques in language lessons students develop acting skills, mainly to:

- portray characters in monologues, improvisations and scripted scenes
- what helps learner in real life situation to read the speaker, the partner;
 - express themselves confidently through movement and gesture – very important for non-verbal communication;
 - communicate character through movement and gesture;
 - participate in blocking (adding movement) to improvised or scripted scenes;
 - understand and execute stage movement effectively;
 - understand and execute stage business effectively;
 - develop a poised, controlled posture .

Reasons to use mime in the language classroom

There are many reasons in favour of using mime activities and techniques in the language classroom. First of all it is entertaining and fun, and can provide motivation to learn. It can provide varied opportunities for different uses of language and because it engages feelings it can provide rich experience of language for the participants. Maley (2005) listed many points supporting the use of mime and drama and these are:

1- It integrates language skills in a natural way. Careful listening is a key feature. Spontaneous verbal expression is integral to most of the activities; and many of them require reading and writing, both as part of the input and the output.

2- It integrates verbal and non verbal aspects of communication, thus bringing together both mind and body, and restoring the balance between physical and intellectual aspects of learning.

3- It draws upon both cognitive and affective domains, thus restoring the importance of feeling as well as thinking.

4- By fully contextualizing the language, it brings the classroom interaction to life through an intensive focus on meaning.

5- The emphasis on whole-person learning and multi-sensory inputs helps learners to capitalize on their strength and to extend their range. In doing so, it offers unequalled opportunities for catering to learner differences.

6- It fosters self-awareness (and awareness of others), self-esteem and confidence; and through this, motivation is developed.

7- Motivation is likewise fostered and sustained through the variety and sense of expectancy generated by the activities.

8- There is a transfer of responsibility for learning from teacher to learners which is where it belongs.

9- It encourages an open, exploratory style of learning where creativity and the imagination are given scope to develop. This, in turn, promotes risk-taking, which is an essential elements in effective language learning

10-It has a positive effect on classroom dynamics and atmosphere, thus facilitating the formation of a bonded group, which learns together.

11-It is an enjoyable experience.

From my point of view, performing real-life situations using mime and gestures in quite beneficial as this promotes pupils practice more speaking skills, develop comprehension and fluency. I think, concentrating too much on grammar rules will not enhance pupils to speak but, conversely, make them be afraid of making mistakes and, consequently, will prevent them from speaking freely.

Using mime and drama activities has clear advantages for language learning. It encourages students to speak, it gives them the chance to communicate, even with limited language, using non-verbal communication, such as body movements and facial expression. There are also a number of other factors which makes drama a very powerful tool in the language classroom.

Drama as a form of mime is an ideal way to encourage learners to guess the meaning of unknown language in a context. Learners will need to use a mixture of language structures and functions ("chunks") if they want to communicate successfully.

Communication cannot be divided into its various components. Mime game can be considered a communicative activity since it fosters communication among learners and provides different opportunities to use the target language in "make believe" situations.

Vernon supports the view that this conversational use of language also promotes fluency. He states that while learning a play or a game, students are encouraged to listen to, potentially read and then repeat their lines over a period of time. By repeating the words and phrases they become familiar with them and are able to say them with increasing fluency by encouraging self-expression, mime activities and participation in mime games motivates students to use language confidently and creatively.

Activity: Using Mime to Show Sentence Meaning

Example of sentence to be mimed: I was walking along the road when a mad dog bit my leg.

1. A student writes these words on the board: . . . *the road . . . bit . . .*
2. He acts out the first action of walking.
3. A partner acts out the second action of the dog bite.
4. The class guesses what the complete sentence is.
5. Another pair of students takes a turn at miming a sentence.

This activity can be varied by having one student, rather than a pair, try to act out the sentence. In a large class, students can work with the sentences in smaller groups so that more are likely to be actively engaged at one time than if the whole class is observing only one or two people.

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